

Effect of Longitudinal Bars Resistance on Crack Spacing in Reinforced Concrete Continuous Beams

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Abstract— This paper presents an experimental study on the effect of longitudinal bars' resistance on crack spacing in hyperstatic reinforced concrete (R/C) continuous beams. The research builds on the theoretical frameworks of Ferry-Borges and Kuczynski, adopted by the CEB, to analyze crack spacing in statically indeterminate beams. Two concrete classes (high and medium compressive strength) were tested on real-scale beams under progressive loading until collapse. The study investigates crack spacing, crack opening, and bending moment at cracking, with results compared to CEB and Kuczynski methods. Findings indicate that the longitudinal bars' resistance significantly influences crack spacing, while their arrangement has no notable effect. A modified Ferry-Borges formula incorporating a correction factor based on the real steel strength is proposed to improve crack spacing predictions.

Keywords— Reinforced concrete, Crack spacing, Longitudinal bars, Continuous beams, Steel resistance

I. INTRODUCTION

In achieving reinforced concrete constructions, depending on the cracking state, the cracks openings are limited to certain predefined values. As it is well known, the excessivity of the concrete cracking constitutes a real and permanent risk for structures and their durability. It becomes important to realize them with the assurance to avoid the deformation and keep a good external aspect. This is assured by the quality of execution conjugated with the steel grade.

From previous decades, the improvement of the used steel grade improves the resistance of the element significantly, but on the other side it generated the formation of cracks which cause a higher risk of failure. This is relatively due to ordinary steel grade used. The cracking is an aleatory phenomenon which occurs in reinforced concrete. Its analysis is carried out with difficulty.

In usual service conditions, the resisting elements subjected to tensile or bending are normally cracked. For these accepted reasons, it becomes necessary to limit the cracks openings to so that the maximal values are not exceeded. In the existing literature, the crack openings and their spacing are bonded tightly. This study considers the CEB method [1-3] and Kuczynsky theory [4-7]. In the latter method, the crack openings are considered a function of the spacing between cracks.

The objective of this research work was to study the effect of the resistance of the longitudinal bar on crack spacing in R/C continuous beams. These tests were conducted by considering two different classes of concretes [8]. The reinforced concrete dimensioning was based on three limit states. They consist of ruin state, limits of strain and of cracking. The analysis of cracked sections considers that they are admitted in II phase. For this, the cracks emergence and spread are regarded as being an admissible state with a condition of limiting their openings. The statically indeterminate beams were realized in real size. They were loaded by concentrated loads of which values were increased progressively from zero until obtaining the collapse. In parallel, the three following parameters were

investigated, namely the cracks opening, bending moment cracking and cracks spacing. The exploitation of the results allowed to analyze the concrete class influence on the cracks spacing [9] and after on the cracks opening [10]. As they are rarely investigated, they are referenced to the experimentations made by Monnier [11] and Kuczynski [4-7] on a single concrete class to treat the problem of the cracks openings. The present study is a continuation of the previous methods and deals with the exploitation of the extracted data to study the longitudinal bars effect on crack spacing.

Given that the present work was carried out in a nonnull shear force situation, it should be interesting to investigate the case where the bending moment is constant with a negligible shear force effect.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, hyperstatic R/C beams were made at real scale. They were of identical dimensions and tested under the loading mode. The two used concrete classes are noted A and B. This choice was made according to the characteristics of compressive strength (high and medium). The bars arrangement conformed to the bending moment diagram and this at the elastic phase.

A. Dimensions and Loading Mode

The reference model used for all the tests is that of Monnier [11] according to both the dimensions of the beams and the method of loading. In this model, single class of concrete was used. However, in the discussed tests, two concrete classes are envisaged to analyze their effect on the spacing between cracks [9]. The tested beams are simply supported at three points equally spaced, with a total length of 4.40 m. Each span has a length of 2.00 m and the two overhangs are of 20 cm of lengths. The cross-section is: 15x26 cm². Four equal charges are applied to the beam as shown in Figure 1 with the loading device. investigations.

Figure. 1 Adopted device for the test.

B. Reinforcement steel bars of the tested beams

The main reinforcement bars are grade T steel of 12 mm diameter. The transverse reinforcement bars are mild steel of 8 mm diameter at spacing of 15 cm. A typical reinforcement is constituted of 2T12 at the top and 3T12 at the bottom as shown in Figure 2.

Figure. 2 Sections of beams in span.

C. Realization of the beams.

The compositions of the different concrete have been carefully realized. The concrete homogeneity is ensured by vibration.

Figure 3. Load transmission device.

Figure 4. Failure mode at *Central support (force sensor)*.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1, gives the average spacing between two successive cracks measured for each beam by the realized tests. Table 2, gives a summary of the experimental and theoretical results based on the percentage of steel and two concretes classes.

TABLE I: EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE CRACK SPACING

Concrete class	Beam category	$l_{f,exp}$ (cm)	$\bar{l}_{f,exp}$ (cm)
A = 40 MPa	AI1	15,27	15,05
	AI2	14,82	
B = 30 MPa	BI1	14,92	14,92
	BI2	/	

TABLE 2: COMPARISON OF THE CRACK SPACING EXPERIMENTALLY OBTAINED WITH THOSE CALCULATED USING THE METHODS OF CEB AND KUCZYNSKI.

Beam Category	$l_{f,the\ CEB}$	$l_{f,the\ Kuczynski}$	Average $l_{f,exp}$
A	7,01 cm	11,87 cm	15,05 cm
B	7,01 cm	11,87 cm	14,92 cm

Given the differences between the theoretical values from the two methods, it is concluded that the obtained experimental values are closer to those of the method Kuczynski (Ferry Borges)[13,12,14]. The evaluation of the cracks spacing is based on the proposed Ferry Borges empirical formula. This later was approved by the CEB 'European concrete Committee. It was experimentally established, on the basis of a nominal empirical strength steel $\sigma_{en} = 3600\text{ kg / cm}^2$. It is expressed in Eq.1:

$$l_f = 1.5d + k_1 \cdot \phi / \omega \tag{1}$$

where:

d : coating thickness of the reinforcement in cm.

ϕ : diameter of a bar (in cm).

ω : percentage of bars reinforcement.

K_1 : numerical coefficient as given in Table 3, depending on the percentage of reinforcement bars (ω). For intermediate values of K_1 , a linear interpolation is required

TABLE 3 : K_1 VALUES

K_1	0.04	0.07	0.16
ω	0.01	0.02	0.03

In the realized experimentation, the feE400 steel grade was used. Still keeping the conformity in bars positions, it was noted that the spacing was identical for all the tested beams. In the preliminary tests concerning the tensile resistance of the steel, their average real limit resistance was found equals to 5620 Kg/cm^2 at collapse, see table 4. In this experiment, it was found that the steel strength plays an important role on the cracks spacing.

TABLE 4 : Tensile strengths of the used grade steel T12

<i>Proof number</i>	<i>Linear mass in kg/m</i>	<i>Apparent elasticity strength in Kg/mm²</i>	<i>Measured tensile strength in Kg/mm²</i>	<i>Elongation at failure in %</i>
1	0.953	56	66	22.5
2	0.950	56	65	22.8
3	0.953	55	64	22.0
4	0.970	57	65	22.8
5	0.949	57	66	22.5

Note: The test results of tensile failure (bars with high adhesion in use in reinforced concrete elements) for the used steel show a constancy of the strength at failure.

The formula in Eq.1 was improved on the on the basis of this experiment using a steel of same nominal strength by considering its real resistance. It is suggested in Eq.2:

$$l_{fz} = 1.5 d + \alpha_z \cdot K_1 \cdot \phi / \omega \tag{2}$$

where α_z is the ratio of the relationship as given in Eq.3

$$\alpha_z = \sigma_{en,real} / \sigma_{en} = 5620 / 3600 = 1.56 \tag{3}$$

It was found that by introducing this ratio as a correcting factor, the crack spacing were much closer to those experimentally obtained relatively to those given by the Ferry Borges formula and used by Kuczynski in his theory on the cracking. This coefficient is based on tensile tests conducted on the used grade steel for bars of 12 cm diameter. The steel bars are of a high bond type. The reached values at failure were reported in Table 4.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study showed that the arrangement of the longitudinal steel bars according to the bending moment has no effect on the crack spacing. But, the resistance of the longitudinal bars plays a significant role on the cracks spacing. Therefore, a suggestion for improving the Ferry Borges expression, approved by the CEB to calculate the cracks spacing was proposed. This consists of introducing a corrector factor in the second term of the Ferry Borges expression which was deduced from an experimentation obtained on the basis of a nominal empirical resistance of the steel bars.

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